

IRIS
Pilots

Artificial Intelligence Threat Reporting and Incident Response System

Securing the smart city's IoT and control systems against confidentiality & integrity breaches

Vulnerable Road Users Detection

City: Barcelona

Goal: To increase safety for VRUs using an edge compute-enabled infrastructure and complemented with AR, 5G, Drones,...

Scenario Stress testing

- Incorrect Data could force TRAM to interrupt its service and/or unexpected risks to VRUs

Possible attacks

- Cabinet break-in
- WiFi hacking
- Denial of Service
- Camera stream hijacking
- SQL Injection
- User impersonation
- Transaction tampering

Securing AI-enabled infrastructure of autonomous transport systems in a smart city

Autonomous Smart Vehicles

City: Tallinn

Goal: Crash autonomous public transportation and fool traffic light system

Scenario Stress testing

- Disrupt ML/AI system through malformed input

Possible attacks

- False Code Injection
- Data Injection
- Denial of Service (DoS)
- Data alteration (Man-in-the-middle)
- Modification of public infrastructure materials
- GPS spoofing
- Broadcast/transaction tampering
- MAC Flooding

Effective incident response and threat intelligence collaboration for critical cross-border smart grid threats

Public Smart Grid Infrastructure

City: Helsinki

Goal: Trigger wrong behaviour of the automated systems on the Smart Grid

Scenario Stress testing

- Feed incorrect data to provoke unexpected behaviour

Possible attacks

- Spoofing (DHCP/ARP), STP
- MAC Flooding
- CDP Manipulation
- Manipulation of register values
- XSS vulnerabilities on infrastructure
- Lack of authentication and encryption
- Modification of device circuits
- Reverse engineering

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Artificial Intelligence Threat Reporting and Incident Response System

Advanced Tools, Services and Network Availability for CERTs/CSIRTs

An EU industry ready for Threats and Challenges in new scenarios: IoT, ICS, AI and other system

A more competitive offering of secure products and services for European Stakeholders in the Digital MarketPlace

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